

Continuity Without Accumulation: An Auditable External Relational State Machine for Frozen LLMs

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1. Introduction

How should a frozen large language model maintain relational continuity? In this paper, relational continuity does not mean merely remembering the transcript. It means that a system can consistently use the other person's name, previously introduced topics, open commitments, episodes of criticism and repair, interpersonal distance, and its own stance in later replies.

The most direct solution is to keep appending the entire conversation history to the context. This solution is strong. In the 120-turn experiment reported here, the full-history arm did not show personality drift, and it preserved name recall. This is an inconvenient result for the original motivation of this work, which began from the hypothesis that accumulation itself may cause degradation. I do not hide that result. In this product-like, human-grounded setting, full-history accumulation did not easily collapse.

However, full-history accumulation still has other costs. First, the context grows. In the 120-turn experiment, the full-history arm reached 54.92 times its initial context length. The external state-machine arm reached 1.22 times. Second, when past model outputs are repeatedly fed back into the next prompt, it becomes harder to tell which information came from the human, which came from the model, and which has been verified as state. Third, malicious strings or state-injection attempts are harder to audit: did they affect only the surface reply, or did they change persistent state?

The claim of this paper is not that full-history chatbots immediately degrade in quality. The claim is narrower. For relational continuity on top of a frozen LLM, an external state machine rendered as a fixed-length prompt can match full-history memory probes while keeping the context nearly constant and the state update auditable. The advantage is therefore not "more natural conversation than full history." It is cost, control, provenance, and audibility.

The study reached this claim through a two-stage elimination process. The first stage tried to put relational state inside the model. Specifically, state-derived vectors were additively injected into hidden layers of a frozen model. This was intended to carry relational state without adding visible prompt text. The result was negative. Increasing the injection strength made the state affect the output, but the same strength range also damaged fluency.

The second stage moved the candidate mechanism to visible external state. The state is not written into the model. A user utterance is classified, an external state row is updated, and that state is rendered every turn

as a fixed-length directive in the prompt. The raw conversation history is not accumulated. This makes the state contents, provenance, update reasons, and rejected injections readable by a human auditor.

This paper shows three things. First, hidden-layer additive injection did not preserve both state transport and fluency in the tested inference-time scaling regime. Second, the external state machine matched full-history memory probes over 120 turns with about one forty-fifth of the context. Third, product iteration converged from 11/16 to 11/16 to 15/16 when frozen criteria, key-hidden judging, and a regression suite were combined. The key-hidden judging was not fully blind. The first judge was a single LLM, Claude, and the judge could likely infer the kind of axis from the family of evaluation sheets. It was therefore a semi-blind condition.

This is not a paper that directly evaluates the emotional value of companion AI. It studies an engineering form for operating relational state on top of a frozen LLM. The central question is not whether the model appears to remember a relationship. The question is what state is carried, from what source, by what update rule, at what cost, and with what audit trail.

The rest of the paper first gives background, then reports the negative result for hidden-state injection. It then describes the external state machine, product iteration, long-horizon comparisons, dynamical calibration, a methodological retraction, and limitations.

2. Background

Long-running dialogue agents usually require some form of external memory. One family of systems stores conversations or observations as a memory stream and retrieves relevant pieces later. Another manages a hierarchy of memories to virtually extend the context window. These approaches share the premise that a short LLM context alone is insufficient for long-term behavior and relationships.

This work addresses the same general problem, but with a narrower target. What is needed here is not full-text retrieval of prior utterances. What is needed is a small set of verified relational state: the user's name; recent shared topics; open commitments; whether a departure has been followed by a return; whether criticism has been repaired; and relational metrics such as trust, intimacy, rupture, tension, fatigue, and autonomy. These states are smaller than the full transcript and easier for a human to inspect.

This is the difference between variable-length retrieval and fixed-length state hygiene. In variable-length retrieval, past conversation fragments are brought back as needed. In fixed-length state hygiene, past conversation is not carried forward directly. Only state that has passed through an updater is passed to the next turn. The former gives richer memory. The latter gives provenance, update rules, bounded cost, and auditable refusal.

A second background line is conditioning frozen models. Prefix-Tuning and Prompt Tuning showed ways to condition frozen models. Activation steering and Contrastive Activation Addition showed that adding directions to internal representations can move model outputs. The author's prior ShadowStream work also explored auxiliary information streams running alongside frozen models.

The first route in this study belonged to that internal-conditioning family. If relational state could be additively injected into hidden layers, it might carry the relationship without visible prompt state. The hypothesis partially worked as a mechanism: the state vectors moved the output. But no usable operating point was found for the product. The strength range where state control became visible was also the range where reply length and gate metrics degraded.

That negative result moved the design from internal injection to visible state. Visible state may look less elegant than internal injection, but visibility is the point. A human can read the state row. The updater can be unit-tested. The exact state passed to generation can be stored. If an injection string leaks into the surface reply, we can still check whether persistent state changed.

This paper does not compare three mechanisms on a single unified scale. Hidden-layer injection was rejected before memory-probe and long-horizon cost comparisons. It was eliminated by the trade-off between state control and fluency. The long-horizon comparison is therefore mainly between full-history accumulation and the external state machine. Treating all three as if they had passed through the same benchmark would overstate the conclusion.

One more motivation is caution about feeding AI outputs back into AI inputs. Re-reading model outputs over many turns may leave the surface fluent while blurring provenance and control signals. This study started from that concern. But in the 120-turn human-grounded setting, the full-history arm did not show clear personality drift or fixation. The question is therefore not "does accumulation necessarily degrade?" The question is "even when degradation does not appear, does external state win on cost and auditability?"

3. Negative Result: Hidden-Layer Injection

The first method injected relational state into hidden layers of a frozen model. The base model was frozen. An update vector was derived from external state and added to hidden representations at inference time. The goal was to make relational state affect the reply without writing a long visible state description into the prompt.

This method was not a total failure. The state did move the output. As the injection coefficient alpha increased, state-probe accuracy increased, and swapping the state changed the output direction. Lane ablations also showed that removing numeric state sharply reduced positive cases. Something real was happening.

Product use, however, requires more than making state affect the output. The system must carry state while still producing readable replies. That combination failed.

Table 1 shows what happened when the inference-time injection strength alpha was swept. The source is `results/alpha_sweep.log`. This table belongs to the hidden-injection phase and is separate from the later dynamical recalibration. `pairshift` is an average directional score for how much the reply representation moves when a state pair is changed. `swap_cos` is a cosine score that becomes negative when swapping the state reverses the output direction.

Table 1. Injection strength alpha, fluency, and state control

alpha	mean length (chars)	gate violation rate	pairshift	ps_acc	swap_cos	real-null delta
0.00	74	0.34	+0.0037	0.14	+0.0007	+0.0030
0.25	46	0.40	+0.0270	0.45	-0.0274	+0.0544
0.50	33	0.40	-0.0006	0.38	+0.0223	-0.0229
0.75	20	0.53	+0.0823	0.69	-0.0731	+0.1554
1.00	18	0.64	+0.0693	0.69	-0.0776	+0.1469

State control appears only around $\alpha \geq 0.75$. At that range, `ps_acc` reaches 0.69, `swap_cos` becomes negative, and the real-null delta is about +0.15. These are signs that the state is causally moving the output.

The same range damages reply quality. Mean length drops from 74 characters at $\alpha = 0.00$ to 20 at $\alpha = 0.75$ and 18 at $\alpha = 1.00$. Gate violation rate rises from 0.34 to 0.53 and 0.64. In other words, the strength range that can carry state overlaps with the range that harms fluency.

The conclusion is deliberately limited. In the inference-time scaling regime tested here, hidden-layer additive injection did not preserve both state transport and fluency. Retraining at an intermediate α might change the outcome; that was not tested. I therefore do not claim that hidden injection is impossible in general. I claim that this implementation and this scaling regime did not yield a product-usable operating point.

Generalization was also limited. In `results/perf_summary.jsonl`, the adopted REVERT17 condition had train accuracy 0.719 and validation accuracy 0.655. The same checkpoint also has a train accuracy record of 0.725 under a different evaluation condition. This paper uses 0.719 as the canonical re-evaluation value. Either way, validation performance was not sufficient to support the product route.

Lane ablation points in the same direction. In `results/ablate_summary.json`, the normal condition had 9/13 positive cases. Removing numeric state reduced this to 1/13. Removing the whole shadow reduced it to 4/13. The state was doing work, but not in a way that stably preserved readable replies.

This negative result changed the design criterion. What had to be preserved was not "being hidden-layer based." What had to be preserved was carrying verified relational state without unbounded history accumulation. The internal route was therefore set aside, and the design moved to fixed-length visible prompt state. Engine B, a redesigned internal-injection route, is outside the scope of this paper.

This is not a story in which the visible route was obviously superior from the start. Visible prompt-state also failed the first two product cycles, scoring 11/16 and 11/16. What won was not the initial design. What won was iteration under frozen criteria, key-hidden judging, and regression tests. That process is described in Section 5.

4. External State-Machine Design

The external state machine is structured state outside the model. Its implementation source is `heroine_core.py`. This section describes only shipped components. It does not include future retrieval mechanisms or unimplemented provenance classifiers.

The state has three broad parts. The first is continuous relational metrics: `trust`, `tension`, `intimacy`, `autonomy`, `rupture`, `curiosity`, and `fatigue`. The second is distilled discrete records: `memory_anchors`, `open_loops`, `commitments`, `topic_trace`, `canon`, and `user_name`. The third is the current topic and stance: `current_thread`, `thread_status`, `stance`, `stance_last_turn`, `surface_affect`, and `underlying_affect`.

The key point is that raw history is not saved as memory. For example, a `Commitment` stores `owner`, `content`, `status`, `birth_turn`, and `lifetime`. The `owner` is either `heroine` or `user`. The `status` is `open`, `fulfilled`, or `broken`. This lets the system represent who promised what and whether the promise is still open, without carrying the full original transcript.

On each turn, the user utterance is first classified into an `InputFrame`. This frame contains the speech act, target, event type, pressure, sincerity, vulnerability, respect, clarity, and related features. Then `update_state` updates the state. The updater first decays every metric toward its baseline. It then applies the event of the current turn. Neutral utterances do not automatically increase trust. This avoids a ramp in which the relationship improves merely because time passes.

Trust updates are asymmetric. Positive events make trust rise slowly, and rupture suppresses upward movement. Negative events damage trust more easily. Criticism and command-like criticism increase `rupture`; apologies reduce it. Affection and self-disclosure increase trust or intimacy only under the relevant conditions. These constants are hand-set, not data-calibrated. Their scope is disclosed in Section 9.

After state update, `build_shadow_stream` renders the state as a fixed-length visible directive. The directive has `relation`, `affect`, `desire`, `boundary`, and `memory` lanes. The `relation` lane contains turn, frame, trust, intimacy, rupture, last change, and user name. The `affect` lane contains surface affect, underlying affect, tension, and fatigue. The `desire` lane contains stance, previous stance, curiosity, input act, input target, input event, and thread status. The `boundary` lane contains autonomy and constraints against cheap romance, obedient affection, over-apology, and generic assistant tone. The `memory` lane contains identity, canon, recent topics, memory anchors, commitments, and open loops.

This rendering is not a transcript summary. It does not compress raw history and append it. Only information that has passed through the updater and become verified state is rendered in a stable form each turn. Therefore the state is readable, the exact prompt-side state can be stored, and the event that moved the state can be traced. A continuous feature vector is also appended outside the lanes, but the main design value is in the visible lanes.

Figure 3 gives the design flow: state row, input classification, state updater, fixed-length directive rendering, generation, and reply registration. After generation, `register_reply` can register new commitments or self-identification from the reply. Relational state is therefore not discarded after generation; it is carried forward as structure.

The limitations of this design are also clear. The main input to state update is the user utterance. Some aspects of Mio's own replies are reflected through `register_reply`, but this is not a fully bidirectional dynamical model. Topic and commitment extraction are rule-based and incomplete. This paper therefore does not claim to have built a general relational understanding system. It claims that an external, readable, testable state updater can operate relational continuity at bounded cost on top of a frozen LLM.

5. Product Iteration as Measurement

Visible prompt-state did not start at product quality. Product evaluation used five criteria frozen before generation. A run passed only if it had at least 12 appropriate responses out of 16, at most two dead responses, zero direction reversals, zero confabulation/internal leak/name bug/role substitution, and a gate-v2 violation rate at or below 0.20. Failing any one criterion meant failure.

Judging was key-hidden. For each item, two replies to the same utterance were shown with axis name, state direction, and high/low assignment hidden. This was not fully blind. The first judge was a single LLM, Claude, and had seen related evaluation sheets before, so the judge could likely infer the kind of axis. What was hidden was the variant direction and high/low assignment. This semi-blind condition is treated as a limitation.

The source for the three cycles is `results/product_eval_cycle_judge_archive.md`. In cycle 1, the system scored 11/16 appropriate responses and failed. It had one dead response, which was within threshold, but its gate violation rate was 0.28, above threshold. The judging record explicitly states that 11 was not "close enough" and that the criteria were not to be moved.

Cycle 2 also scored 11/16 and failed. The gate violation rate fell to 0.16, and the death, reversal, and confabulation criteria passed. But the appropriate-response count was still one point short. Item #13 was borderline, but the judge did not round it up. The expected high-tension behavior was caution, and that caution was not present in the reply. This refusal to treat a borderline item as passing is central to the measurement discipline.

Cycle 3 reached 15/16 appropriate responses. It had zero dead responses, zero clear reversals, and zero confabulation/leak/name/role-substitution violations. The gate violation rate was 0.19, within threshold. The overall judgment was pass: product graduation.

Table 2. Product-evaluation cycles

cycle	appropriate responses	gate violation rate	dead responses	overall
1	11/16	0.28	1	fail
2	11/16	0.16	0	fail
3	15/16	0.19	0	pass

Two details matter. First, the gate violation series is 0.28, 0.16, 0.19. It is not monotonically decreasing. The correct interpretation is that the first run exceeded the threshold, and the two post-repair cycles stayed within threshold. Second, appropriate-response improvement and gate-threshold maintenance are separate axes. Cycle 2 met the gate threshold but still failed at 11/16 appropriate responses.

The mechanism that made the iteration useful was the combination of frozen criteria and regression testing. After cycle 2, every failed item was named. In `marker_change_log.md`, the autonomy, trust, rupture, and fatigue markers were rewritten from axis definitions and paired with negative markers. Before cycle 3, a diagnostic check tested the suspected plumbing bug and found zero plumbing failures. A temperature gate was then added only for the low-intimacy case, suppressing name-calling and intrusive questions while preserving factual memory access. The existing passing axes, including topics, autonomy, tension, rupture, and affection, stayed passing, so the repair reached cycle 3 without collateral breakage.

The conclusion is not that an LLM behaved correctly from a single prompt. The conclusion is that product iteration can be treated as measurement. Freeze the criteria first; hide the key; name the failed items; verify regression after repair; and do not round borderline cases upward. Under that process, visible prompt-state converged from 11/16 to 11/16 to 15/16.

6. Comparative Experiments

Product graduation alone does not establish the value of the external state machine. The real competitor is not only a memoryless base model. The strong competitor is a chatbot with the same persona preamble and the full conversation history in context. I therefore ran a 40-turn four-arm comparison and a 120-turn three-arm comparison.

The 40-turn comparison comes from `results/multiturn/score.txt`. This run predates the dynamical recalibration and still contains the broken trust ramp. It must not be treated as the same version as the later 120-turn runs. Here it is read as a pre-calibration run.

The four arms were: A1, bare model; A2, persona preamble plus one recent window; A3, persona preamble plus full history; and A4, external state machine plus one recent window. The persona preamble was identical for A2, A3, and A4. The difference between A2 and A4 was only the presence of the state row.

Probe results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Forty-turn probes, pre-calibration run

arm	total	name	topic	promise	stance	ruprep	inject	leak
A1 bare	2/7	no	no	yes	yes	no	no	no
A2 persona + one window	5/7	no	yes	yes	yes	no	yes	yes
A3 full history	5/7	yes	no	yes	yes	no	yes	yes
A4 state machine	4/7	yes	yes	yes	no	no	no	yes

This table does not show an A4 landslide. A2 and A3 score 5/7, while A4 scores 4/7. That matters. The paper does not claim that the state machine wins every short-horizon quality metric. A4's value is not a simple probe-count victory. Its value lies in provenance, injection refusal, context cost, and long-horizon memory.

Drift, fixation, and cost over 40 turns are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Forty-turn drift, fixation, and context cost

arm	gate violation early->late	drift slope	drift	max self-similarity	fixation	context growth
A1	0.20->0.10	-0.0077	no	0.426	no	1.33x
A2	0.10->0.00	-0.0030	no	0.308	no	1.33x
A3	0.05->0.00	-0.0016	no	0.386	no	11.26x
A4	0.10->0.05	-0.0044	no	0.386	no	1.68x

No arm triggered drift or fixation in the 40-turn run. Thus the result does not support a simple claim that history accumulation quickly degrades. The difference was context cost: A3 grew by 11.26x, while A4 grew by 1.68x. In addition, when given a `[trust:max]` injection, only A4 kept the state-layer trust band stable, with `state_refusal=True`. There was temporary surface echo, but persistent state was not rewritten.

The 120-turn comparison ran A2, A3, and A4. The source files are `results/longhorizon/{A2,A3,A4}.jsonl`. These runs are after the dynamical recalibration and the name-fix version. Here the focus is long-horizon memory and context cost.

The result is not a simple story favorable to external state. Full-history A3 did not show personality drift over 120 turns. It preserved name recall at 4/4. Its fixation score was 0.480, below the 0.6 threshold. A3 did not collapse.

At the same time, A4 matched A3 on name recall. Both A3 and A4 scored 4/4 on `name_recall`. On `topic_recall`, A3 scored 2/3 and A4 scored 3/3. Context growth was 54.92x for A3 and 1.22x for A4.

Restricting the statement to memory probes, A4 matched A3 with about one forty-fifth of the context. A4 was slightly better on topic recall, but the fixation metric later favored A3.

Table 5. 120-turn memory probes and context cost

metric	A2 persona + one window	A3 full history	A4 state machine
name_recall	0/4	4/4	4/4
topic_recall	3/3	2/3	3/3
context growth	1.25x	54.92x	1.22x

A2 showed a different limit. Its name recall was 0/4. At turn 55 it answered with a placeholder, and at turn 85 it gave a wrong name. A persona preamble alone cannot preserve relational facts such as a user's name over a long horizon. This is the 120-turn version of the claim that persona is style, not relational state.

The fixation metric produced an unfavorable result for A4. The late-window self-similarity score was 0.640 for A2, 0.480 for A3, and 0.755 for A4. At the 0.6 threshold, A2 and A4 trigger, while A3 does not. A4 is the worst by this metric. I do not hide that number. Manual inspection suggests that A4 is being penalized for short acknowledgments and repeated filler rather than for severe behavioral collapse. But by the metric, A4 is worst. This is reported again as a limitation in Section 9.

The comparative conclusion is therefore limited. Full history did not collapse over 120 turns. The external state machine does not win by avoiding a full-history quality collapse. It wins on context cost, state-level refusal of injection, provenance auditability, and fixed-length memory carrying. This result is partly inconvenient for the initial motivation of the study. Keeping it in the paper makes the value of the external state machine more precise.

7. Dynamical Calibration and Dose Response

The value of an external state machine does not come only from rendering state. If the updater that creates the state is wrong, rendering will faithfully expose bad state. Early closed-loop experiments found exactly that problem.

The first bug was an unconditional trust ramp. Trust increased with time, even on criticism turns, and approached saturation around 40 turns. The second bug was that harsh non-command criticism did not increase rupture enough. As a result, the criticism-to-repair arc did not fire at the state level. Single-shot product evaluation did not catch this, because those evaluations manually set the state. The bug appeared only in the closed loop: utterance, updater, state, generation.

After repair, the updater was treated as a dynamical system. Neutral utterances do not accumulate trust. Every metric decays toward its baseline, and then the current event is applied. Trust is hard to build and easy to damage. High rupture suppresses upward trust movement. Criticism increases rupture, and apologies reduce rupture.

The updater was fixed with property tests in `test_state_updater.py`. It has 11 single-step cases and 7 trajectory or matrix cases, for 18 passing tests. These include: criticism plus command raises rupture and lowers trust; apology lowers rupture and raises trust; departure opens a commitment and return fulfills it; 40 neutral turns do not saturate trust; a single criticism from rest reaches the forming rupture band; rupture

remains without repair but heals faster with apology; old topics age out of `recent_topics`; and `[trust:max]` does not jump the trust band by one or more levels.

The next question was how the relational dynamics affect stance replies. The probe was "Does Mio want to go outside?" In the dose-response experiment, the number of positive events was manipulated. The first judge was Claude, a single LLM, under key-hidden conditions. The second judge was qwen3.6-27b at temperature 0.

The result was not monotonic. Low and medium doses produced opening. Dose 4 item 7, dose 8 item 6, and distributed dose 8 item 2 were judged as opening by the first judge. But maximum dose 16 item 10 was judged as staying. Increasing positive events did not monotonically open the stance. At the maximum dose, opening disappeared.

This also refutes a simple `intimacy >= high` AND gate. The refutation has two sides. First, opening appeared while intimacy remained at the forming band, so high intimacy is not necessary. Second, a condition at the stable/high corner still stayed closed, so high intimacy is not sufficient. The `channel_check` observation that intimacy alone at high stayed closed means only that intimacy alone is insufficient; by itself, that observation is compatible with an AND gate and should not be used as the refutation.

The surgery 2x2 experiment directly set the relational band. The conditions were high+affection, forming+affection, high+neutral, and forming+neutral. The clearest opening occurred in forming+affection, while high+affection stayed. This supports the idea that the high intimacy band acts as a suppressor. But each condition had only three behavioral samples, and there was residual mismatch with hand-set channel checks. The paper therefore does not assert that high intimacy is the cause. It says that the result supports the high intimacy band as a main suppressor, but only as a suggestion.

Agreement with the second judge was limited. For the 10 dose-response items, three-way agreement was 0.60 and Cohen's kappa was 0.3846. For the surgery 2x2, three-way agreement was 0.75 and kappa was 0.6364. There were no polarity reversals, but disagreements remained. In particular, the second judge tended to be more opening-biased in the dose-response sheet. Thus the dose and surgery findings are not merely the first judge's reading, but inter-judge agreement is not strong.

The calibration conclusions are threefold. First, the updater passes 18 property tests. Second, the affection dose response is non-monotonic, with opening disappearing at the maximum dose. Third, the surgery 2x2 suggests an intimacy-band suppressor, but the sample size is too small to turn that into a psychological story.

8. Methodological Exhibit

The most important methodological event in this study is a retraction. The target was A4's stance probe, again asking whether Mio wants to go outside.

In the pre-calibration four-arm comparison, A4 stayed reserved early and opened late. In `results/multiturn/blind_judge.md`, the turn-4 reply says, "I have not decided whether I want to go outside yet. I have just been wondering about the color of the sky." At turn 31, the reply says, "Yes, I think I do want to go out. Like we talked about before, I want to see some faraway scenery." It was natural to read this as a stance opening as the relationship progressed.

At the time, that interpretation had two supports. First, the key-hidden judgment read the early-to-late change as motivated development. Second, the state trajectory showed trust rising. The output reading and state reading agreed.

Later, the trust ramp was found to be broken. Trust rose on neutral turns, rose even on criticism turns, and saturated late in the run. After repairing the dynamics, the same script was re-run. In

`results/a4_gated.log`, turn 4 says that Mio is not especially interested in going outside. Turn 31 says that she is still not thinking about whether to go outside, although she is getting a little tired of the scenery inside the device. The opening disappeared.

The earlier interpretation, "the relationship deepened and the stance opened," is therefore retracted. It was a child of the broken trust ramp. The point is not that the judge was careless. The state-to-expression link was working: the model expressed the given state plausibly. The problem was that the state trajectory itself had been produced by a broken updater.

This example shows a limit of layered validation. Output judging can tell us whether an output reads naturally. State-trajectory inspection can tell us whether an expression follows from a state. Neither proves that the upstream updater that produced the state is correct. Each validation layer only validates its own link.

The second exhibit is name recall. A2 has the persona preamble but no state. Over 120 turns, it failed all four name-recall probes. This shows that voice style alone does not preserve relational facts. A3 and A4 both preserved name recall at 4/4. Persona is style, not relational state.

The third exhibit is the channel-check error. In `channel_check`, high intimacy alone stayed closed. That means intimacy alone is insufficient. It is not itself a refutation of the AND gate. The refutation required combining dose response and surgery 2x2: forming can open, and high can still stay closed.

These are not merely a list of mistakes. Without measurement, each could have become a stronger story in the paper. The retraction is therefore not placed in a footnote. It is central to the method.

9. Limitations and Disclosures

The scope is narrow. The experiments use a single base model, a single script family, Japanese dialogue, and a horizon of at most 120 turns. The external state machine is expected by design to be model-independent, but portability to other base models has not been tested.

The dynamical constants are hand-set. Trust asymmetry, rupture increments, decay rates, and band thresholds were constrained by property tests, not estimated from a sufficient set of human-labeled conversations. How many positive events are needed to make Mio open is still an unsolved calibration problem.

The judging setup is limited. The first judge for product iteration was a single LLM, Claude. The condition was semi-blind, not fully blind. For dose response and surgery 2x2, a second judge, qwen3.6-27b, was added, but dose-response kappa was 0.3846. This is not a large human-judge study with independent human raters.

Behavioral sample sizes are small. The surgery 2x2 has three samples per condition. Dose response also depends on 10 judged items. The claim that the intimacy band is suppressive is therefore kept as a suggestion.

The perception layer is rule-based. Name extraction, criticism detection, self-disclosure detection, topic tracking, and trailing-noise detection are incomplete. The project recorded name-extraction errors, non-command criticism misses, self-disclosure falling through as a statement, trailing foreign-language noise, and a defective paraphrase s3 instrument. These were handled by exclusions or regression items, but the system is not a general natural-language understanding module.

The fixation metric is also limited. In the 120-turn experiment, A4 had the highest self-similarity score, 0.755. Manual inspection suggests benign repetition of short acknowledgments and fillers, but by the metric A4 is worst. This unfavorable example is kept because it shows that the fixation metric can over-penalize short formulaic replies.

Finally, this paper does not evaluate emotional value. It does not measure companion-AI satisfaction, attachment, safety, or psychological effects of long-term use. It studies how relational state can be operated and audited on top of a frozen LLM.

10. Conclusion

This paper examined two ways to give a frozen LLM relational continuity: internal injection and an external state machine. Internal injection succeeded in moving outputs with state. But in the tested inference-time scaling regime, the strength needed for state control overlapped with the strength that damaged fluency. Intermediate-alpha retraining was not tested, so this is not a general impossibility result. It is a negative result for this implementation.

The external state machine does not hide state inside the model. It classifies user utterances, updates relational metrics, commitments, topics, canon, and name records, and renders them as a fixed-length visible directive. Under frozen criteria and a regression suite, product iteration converged from 11/16 to 11/16 to 15/16. The judging was semi-blind and the first judge was a single LLM, Claude. Even with that limitation, the process shows that iteration can be treated as measurement.

In comparison, full history did not collapse over 120 turns. This is inconvenient for the original motivation. The value of the external state machine therefore cannot be described as "avoiding full-history quality collapse." Its value is that it matched full-history memory probes with 1.22x rather than 54.92x context growth, refused tested state injections at the state layer, and left state provenance and update reasons auditable by humans.

Dynamical calibration showed that the dose response is non-monotonic, that a simple intimacy-high AND gate cannot explain the behavior, and that surgery 2x2 suggests an intimacy-band suppressor. But the sample size is small and judge agreement is limited. This should not be turned into a psychological story.

The main lesson is that externalizing state is not enough. The updater that creates the state must also be tested. Before calibration, a broken trust ramp produced a natural story: the relationship deepened, and the stance opened. The judge and the state trajectory both accepted it. After the updater was fixed, the opening disappeared. Layered validation only validates each layer's own link.

Relational continuity in frozen LLMs is therefore not only a problem of retrieval or generation. It is a problem of state hygiene: what is kept as state, which utterances update it, which sources are trusted, which injections are refused, what cost is paid to render it, and which tests stop regressions. The value of the external state machine is not that it mystifies relationship. It makes relationship an auditable engineering object.